

GEOCHEMISTRY OF WATER-SOLUBLE SALTS IN IRRIGATED SOILS

Muhammadno'monjon Iqrorjon o'g'li Aktamov

PhD Candidate, Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14551369>

Abstract

This research explores the composition and distribution of water-soluble salts in the genetic horizons of irrigated meadow-saz soils. Based on dry residue levels, these soils are categorized as moderately to strongly saline. Using the concentrations of water-soluble ions, hypothetical salts were determined. The analysis highlights that sulfate salts are predominant, and the salinity levels are significantly influenced by mineralized groundwater with a saz regime.

Keywords: salinity, hypothetical salts, geochemical analysis, water extraction, dry residue, sulfate salts.

Introduction

In the 1930s, extensive soil studies were conducted in Central Asia to identify and develop lands suitable for irrigation. These efforts focused on analyzing the composition of soil, parent materials, and groundwater, as well as the distribution of soluble salts across various geomorphological regions. These studies laid the groundwork for landscape-geochemical analysis and enabled the classification of soils based on their salinity and reclamation potential.

Today, in arid regions such as Central Fergana, the study of water-soluble salt geochemistry is essential. These investigations provide insights into combating secondary salinization, justifying large-scale reclamation projects, and advancing sustainable irrigation practices.

Geochemical Dynamics in Saline Soils

Salinity in arid regions arises from geochemical processes that mobilize and accumulate salts. These processes involve interactions between mobile ions, including Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , and HCO_3^- . Salt deposition occurs primarily in response to evaporation exceeding precipitation, particularly in areas with poor drainage systems.

Key Stages of Salt Migration

1. **Mobilization:** Transformation of salts into soluble forms for easy transport.
2. **Migration:** Movement of salts through water flow.
3. **Accumulation:** Deposition of salts in fixed forms within the soil profile.

In arid landscapes, these processes are accelerated by factors such as rising groundwater levels, irrigation, and fertilization practices.

Predominant Salts and Their Characteristics

Irrigated meadow-saz soils contain various soluble salts, as shown in **Table 1**:

Meadow-Saz Soils	Formula	Solubility
Sodium bicarbonate	NaHCO_3	Highly soluble
Magnesium sulfate	$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Highly soluble
Gypsum	$\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Sparingly soluble
Mirabilite	$\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Highly soluble
Sodium chloride	NaCl	Highly soluble

The accumulation of these salts can occur in both lateral and vertical directions, leading to significant deposits over geological timescales. These deposits are particularly prevalent in arid and semi-arid regions.

Findings

Distribution of Salts

In the irrigated soils of Central Fergana, sulfate salts dominate the salinity profile. **Calcium sulfate (CaSO_4)** is the most prevalent, followed by **magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4)**, **sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3)**, and **sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4)**. Groundwater plays a significant role in shaping these distributions, as illustrated in **Table 2**:

Meadow-Saz Soils	(cm)	HCO_3^-	Cl^-	SO_4^{2-}	Ca^{2+}	Mg^{2+}	Na^+
0-30	1.010	-	-	-	-	-	-
30-45	1.238	-	-	-	-	-	-
45-87	1.301	-	-	-	-	-	-

Impact of Irrigation

Continuous irrigation alters the soil's hydrological and salinity dynamics. While irrigation boosts crop productivity, it can also exacerbate secondary salinization if drainage systems are insufficient. Older irrigated soils show increased salt accumulation in deeper layers, highlighting the need for improved irrigation management.

Conclusion

Effective salinity management in irrigated soils involves addressing both natural and human-induced factors. In arid climates like Central Fergana, strategies such

as proper irrigation scheduling, advanced drainage systems, and targeted fertilization are crucial for maintaining soil health and agricultural productivity.

References:

1. Abdurakhmonov, N.Yu., et al. (2023). Properties of irrigated meadow-saz soils of Central Fergana.
2. Turdaliyev, A.T., & Akhunov, A.A. (2022). Ways to increase cotton yield on irrigated meadow-saz soils.
3. FAO. Global Soil Salinity and Management Strategies.
4. Isakov, V.Yu. (1993). Formation and rational use of gypsum-bearing soils.
5. Zokirova, S.Kh. (2017). Soil genesis and agricultural productivity in Central Fergana.
6. Kamilov, O.K. (1992). Properties of carbonate-gypsum soils in Uzbekistan.
7. Mirzaev, U.B. (2017). Soil salinity dynamics in meadow-saz soils.
8. Stepanov, L.P. (1988). Soil temperature dynamics and crop germination.
9. Turdaliyev, A.T. (2019). Morphological features of irrigated soils.
10. Jobborov, B.T., et al. (2021). Soil remediation techniques.
11. Haydarov, M.M. (2020). Humic substances in light sierozem soils.
12. Jabbarov, Z.A. (2019). Agricultural soil improvement techniques.
13. Isaqov, V.Yu. (2020). Environmental changes in Fergana Valley soils.
14. O'tayev, M.S., et al. (2022). Properties of irrigated gray-meadow soils of Syrdarya region.
15. FAO. Guidelines for sustainable soil management.